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THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN MODERN LIFE.

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Annotation:

English is used for more purposes. It is closely related to economic modernization, industrial development and today's social life. Companies compete fiercely for customers while employees compete with each other for their jobs, Student's entry into a professional language environment certainly contributes to the intensification. The English language is rich in scientific and technical features. Foreign languages, especially many of these special words, are related to international words. In order to educate students' interest in the subject of "Foreign language" and to form them, the teacher should not interfere in the motivation field of students, but should learn to control it. The teacher should think about the problem of continuous formation. Motivation among students plays an important role as one of the main tasks of their activity.

Keywords: business, foreign language, career, motivation, educational institutions, economic terms, English, German, French and Russian, modernization.

In today's world, learning a foreign language is one of the most important components of a modern, successful person. Knowing at least one foreign language broadens a person's outlook, allows to learn the culture and traditions of other peoples. It seems that every person wants to be successful in business. And in this case, knowing a foreign language can still be very useful. Firstly, this is additional knowledge, and secondly, employers are more willing to hire a specialist who speaks a foreign language. The main point is the opportunity to plunge into the mysterious and incomprehensible world, it is the opportunity to communicate with people with a different worldview and mentality.

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Materials and methods: It is common to learn English as the international equivalent of communication. But this does not reduce the importance of learning other foreign languages. Perhaps someone will be angry and say that not everyone can learn a foreign language. Yes! Unfortunately, the ability of each society is bright individual, someone has a tendency to exact sciences, someone has a more humanistic thinking. But, of course, every person has abilities, and hardly anyone would disagree with this fact. The most important thing is to develop, nourish and strengthen these abilities. There are many ways to learn foreign languages today. You can be offered an individual approach and a unique development of foreign language lessons. Of course, navigating the endless stream of information alone can be overwhelming. Choosing from all that modern technology has to offer can be overwhelming. However, there are more standard ways of learning a language - it's going to English courses, it's visiting specialized educational institutions, and finally, these are lessons with a tutor.

Anyone who wants to learn a foreign language can choose the most affordable and best option to learn the language they like the most. True, sometimes it is not really necessary to choose, and it is necessary to learn a certain language for some objective reasons, that is, there may be a desire to go to a certain country or to work in some kind of job where one of the conditions is present. Currently, English language plays an important role in various areas of life. This applies to entertainment, education, travel and professional activities. It goes without saying that knowing corporate English for business is a way to expand your opportunities, explore uncharted paths and make new business contacts. Why should people who run their own business know English? Many professions have a direct relationship with foreign languages, there are practically no restrictions. Even if the profession does not require mandatory ability to speak a second language, such knowledge can still be important for the employee himself, because they significantly expand the choice of available vacancies not only in your city and country also abroad . For many, this is a big step towards achieving their professional goals and even starting their own business. You understand that by knowing a foreign language you can move up the career ladder, you can imagine everything you can do with language skills, where you can visit, what you can try and what you can come to, speak, write. Business English is more than just interviewing and CV writing. When you enter the business stream, you have to make presentations, negotiate, answer phone calls, write official letters and business correspondence, sign contracts, etc. Another specific feature of the business language is the level of professional knowledge, then it is necessary not only to know the name of the term, but also to understand it and use it

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correctly. In order to avoid a distorted interpretation of concepts, it is worth learning business English directly at the workplace or during education related to a narrow specialty. Learning a foreign language is directly related to the change of the linguistic view of the world and the way of thinking of the individual. In order to understand a person who speaks another language at an elementary level, it is necessary to take into account the cultural and religious characteristics that we learn and accept along with grammar and vocabulary during the course of a foreign language. And maybe knowing the basic level of spoken English is enough to say hello, book a room in a hotel, have dinner in a restaurant. But if you are an employee of an international company, a business coach, a future entrepreneur, you will have to deal with the use of "foreign" words every day in your professional activities.

Words of foreign language origin are found in the field of supply, management, in the preparation of an advertising campaign, in showing the necessary characteristics of the range, in the study of accounting methodology, and in the experience of industrial and commercial enterprises. In particular, knowledge of the English language is important in evaluating the quality of products, conducting expertise, and compiling written characteristics of supplied products [3]. In the process of teaching this specialty, it is known that students have difficulty in using and interpreting the necessary economic terms. Teachers of the specialty "Commodity science and quality expertise of consumer goods" carry out work on the repetition of learned terms and the compilation of dictionaries containing professional terms in order to master and improve the quality of knowledge in order to acquire a future profession, which increases their level of knowledge.

The process of teaching a foreign language: English is being used for more purposes than ever. It is closely related to economic modernization and industrial development. Companies compete fiercely for customers while employees compete with each other for their jobs, Student's entry into a professional language environment certainly contributes to the intensification. The English language is rich in scientific and technical features. Foreign languages, especially many of these special words, are related to international words. In order to educate students' interest in the subject of "Foreign language" and to form them, the teacher should not interfere in the motivation field of students, but should learn to control it. The teacher should think about the problem of continuous formation. Motivation among students plays an important role as one of the main tasks of their activity. As for international consulting companies, these are primarily the so-called ones. Knowing three or four languages in these

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companies will not surprise anyone: each of the companies has language centers where employees are trained in English, German, French and Russian. Depending on which group of experts from other countries he works with. Some positions require candidates to have written skills. However, the need to learn a foreign language is still very much in question. A large number of university students who do not speak a language, many students believe that a foreign language is necessary. A foreign language plays an important role in the formation of modern specialists, and knowledge has become a necessary part of professional training. To meet the high demands of modern society is not only to be a professional in your field, but also to be able to speak a foreign language fluently.

The role of foreign language in our life: After reading a lot of reference literature on the use of a foreign language in our lives, I learned that 1.5 billion people in the world speak English and another billion are learning it. Today, English is the third most spoken language, followed by Chinese and Spanish. India and China are ahead in terms of the number of people who use English as a second language. Knowing English, maybe the whole world will understand you, which shows the importance of the language. Foreign language is used in many areas of our life: Tourism, travel. English is the language of international communication. If you like to travel, then knowing English will allow you to communicate freely in almost any country and read information signs without difficulty.

Business, career: English is the language of business and you need to know:

- business people who want to enter the international market;
- work in international companies;
- in employment, because today many companies closely cooperate with foreign mail.

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Motivation among students plays an important role as one of the main tasks of their activity.

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